

MEDICAL SCIENCES

UDC 378.147:614.253:616-053.2

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17687321>*

THE LEVEL OF READINESS OF PEDIATRIC STUDENTS FOR INDEPENDENT PRACTICAL ACTIVITY AS AN INDICATOR OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Abstract.

The article presents the results of the analysis of comparative self-assessment of graduating students regarding their readiness for independent work. They assessed their readiness to work with children, taking into account the knowledge gained from the discipline "pediatrics, childhood infections".

Keywords: *children, self-esteem, pediatrics*

Present-day conditions of reforming the system of public health require necessary improvement in the field of training medical staff [1]. Nowadays the aim of a higher educational institution is not only teaching specialists who obtained qualitative training, but development of principally new information-communication technologies and fulfillment of active management for successful competition in the sphere of education [2,3].

The representatives of higher medical institutions are facing a complicated task: to prepare students for independent medical work, to teach them to make decisions in extreme situations, that is, stimulated their clinical thinking, activate creative potential, form continuous interest to learning and future profession

An integrated pattern of innovation technologies in teaching assumes an active student's participation in the process of learning, formation of essential skills and knowledge to apply them under different real conditions, broadening horizons of information space for a future doctor, ability to work in a team and desire for continuous improvement [4]. A timely direction of the innovation pattern in education is imitative and task-oriented learning based on imitation-gaming simulation under conditions of those processes that happen in reality, and particular those introduced into the educational process at the Department of Pediatrics and Children Infectious Diseases, Higher State Educational Establishment of Ukraine "Bukovinian State Medical University".

Objective: to estimate the efficacy of training 5th and 6th-years students specialized in "Pediatrics" on the subject "Pediatrics, Children Infectious Diseases".

Methods. On the basis of the Department of Pediatrics and Children Infectious Diseases, Higher State Educational Establishment of Ukraine "Bukovinian State Medical University" a comparative assessment of

training efficacy of 80 5th and 6th-year students specialized in "Medicine" on the subject "Pediatrics, Children Infectious Diseases" was conducted. The first group included 36 5th-year students specialized in "Pediatrics" (contract form of education - 58,8% students), II group included 44 6th-year students specialized in "Medicine" (contract form of education - 53,3% students).

The students studied according to the credit-module system with application of certain elements of problem-oriented learning. All the students were suggested to participate in the anonymous poll by means of the questionnaire containing 16 questions dealing with the methods of teaching the subject "Pediatrics, Children Infectious Diseases", as well as the attitude of students to teaching, its forms and methods, application of new information resources, individual self-esteem of readiness to professional work.

The results obtained were processed statistically on the personal computer using the package of applied programs "Statistica 5.0".

Results and discussion. While estimating a probable style of their future work 27,3% of students from II group express their desire to work in a team, while in I group only 11,1% ($p > 0,05$) of students preferred this kind of work. 33,3% of students from II group and 11,1% ($p < 0,05$) from I group preferred to work independently without external interference. The necessity to be a "generator of ideas" was marked by 18,2% of the respondents from II group and 22,2% ($p > 0,05$) respondents from I group. 21,2% students from II group and 55,6% ($p < 0,05$) students from I group preferred to work as a subordinate with tasks assuming the display of one's own initiative. The parameters of the risk to be ready to work independently among the 6th-year students on specialty "Medicine" in comparison with

the 5th-year students were higher and constituted: relative risk – 3,0 (95%CI: 2,3 – 3,8) with odds ratio – 3,9 (95%CI: 1,8 – 8,4).

Self-realization and implementation of interests and skills in future profession was marked by 33,3% and 36,3% respondents from I and II groups respectively. At the same time, the possibility to become an independent and unassisted personality at the expense of one's own realization in the future profession was emphasized by 45,5% respondents from II group and only one fifth (22,2%, $p < 0,05$) of the representatives from I group.

A subjective assessment of the level of being informed concerning future profession showed that more than a half of students from II group (54,5%) noted rather high level of obtained knowledge although without own practical experience, contrary to those 33,3% ($p < 0,05$) respondents from I group. The obtained results are likely to be associated with increase of practical hours on learning Pediatrics at the 6th year, and therefore creation of conditions for better training of future specialists on the subject "Pediatrics, Children Infectious Diseases", maturity of clinical thinking at the expense of implementation of the elements form the problem-oriented learning and improvement of professional motivation of graduate students. The parameters of the risk of better self-esteem in professional training in Pediatrics among the 6th-year students in comparison with the 5th-year students were the following: relative

risk - 1,6 (95% CI: 1,2-2,2) with odds ratio - 2,4 (95% CI: 1,3-4,2).

Conclusions. The parameters of the risk to be ready to work independently among the 6th-year students on specialty "Medicine" in comparison with the 5th-year students were higher and constituted: relative risk – 3,0 (95%CI: 2,3 – 3,8) with odds ratio – 3,9 (95%CI: 1,8 – 8,4), the risk of better self-esteem in professional training in Pediatrics: relative risk - 1,6 (95% CI: 1,2-2,2) with odds ratio - 2,4 (95% CI: 1,3-4,2).

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